

DESIGNING 3D PAGEFLIP PROFESSIONAL ON CORE STABILITY AND RADIOACTIVITY FOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT

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Abstract

Technology continues to grow including into the field of education that can be seen with the game educative which is an innovation that combines education and technology. This article focuses on the technique of designing physics electronics module using 3D PageFlip Professional with the final look that can be accessed via computer and android. The electronic physics module used is a 3D Pageflip Professional-based research and development module that requires handouts in PDF format as the basis for making multimedia-based handouts on Core Stability and Radioactivity materials. In this electronic module researchers use open source media such as video, images, flash and animation so that makes this media look interesting for high school students. The result of the project will be published in 3DP format to be read with 3D Pageflip Reader which can be installed in android Operating System and exe format to be read with windows system in personal computer.

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1. Introduction

The development of Information Technology-based teaching materials is one of the research trends in the world of education, including physics. In Physics, the integration of Information Technology has become a necessity, because it is proven to help the learning process become more effective and ultimately can improve students' understanding. Through the help of Information Technology, teachers can apply something that related to Physics, such as research on 3D Pageflip Professional in integration with android on radioactive that greatly attracts interest from readers of radioactive handouts [1]. In the research related to 3D Pageflip Professional, which is displayed on the website is also very interesting [2].

In the next research concerning the development of inquires based learning modules as a whole has been a decent and effective modules that can be use for third year high schoolers for learning independently, this is seen from the test of the user worthiness and evaluation module in terms of finding problems, formulating problems, formulating hypothesis, collecting data, test the hypothesis and forming a conclusions. Discovery-inquiry-based modules get positive responses from students. Almost all research sample students expressed satisfaction and got positive results from discovery-inquiry-based modules [3].

The level of education in Indonesia is still in the stage of improvement or development. In fact, according to The Learning Curve, Indonesia's quality education ranks last out of 40 countries [4]. The development of science and technology plays a major role in education. The role of technology in education can support the learning process, where using this technology can make the learning process effective and efficient.

From "Trends in International Math and Science" conducted by the Global Institute in 2007 showed that only 5% of students in Indonesia were able to work on reasoning problems in the high category, where students in Korea could reach 71%. Otherwise, 78% of students in Indonesia can work on low category memorization problems, while Korean students only 10% [5].

According to Arsyad, the development of information and communication technology encouraged to find some efforts in the use of technological results in the learning process [6]. Therefore, as a task carried out by a teacher is able to use the tools provided by the school or even creatively and innovatively able to use inexpensive and efficient tools to help achieve learning goals.

The results of the needs analysis through interviews with one teacher at 66 senior high school Jakarta, she said that one of the most difficult material to be taught in teaching physics was the material of Core Stability and Radioactivity. The efforts made by her in handling the material is only utilizing Power Point and the Internet. In developing the media on Core Stability and Radioactivity, she hoped that there would be an interactive media with an attractive, clear appearance, accompanied by appropriate experiments and evaluations.

Based on research in modules usage, scientific literacy is assessed from four points, that is : Science process, scientific knowledge, science application, and the attitude of students to science. Assessment of scientific literacy of students in all points shows an increase in each meeting. The average value of the scientific process of students is good. The average value participant in science knowledge is very good. The average value of students' application of science is very good. The attitude of students towards science is in the good. More than 85% students have fulfilled the level of classical achievement set [7].

Module development is needed in providing the learning media. The results of research on the development of learning modules are based on guided inquiry on materials, the average validation performed by experts is 81.68%. The module validation that has been developed is seen from content validity, construct validity, and language validity [8]. In addition, based on the results of assessments conducted by media experts, material experts and learning resource experts and the results of trials conducted on teachers and students, showed that the visual-based physics module developed was very good, so it was suitable to be used as an independent teaching material by high school students [9]. After proper validation and testing, it is concluded that the development of the e-module for long distance education has met the criteria to be used as learning media in the Department of Electrical Engineering in State University of Malang [10].

3D PageFlip Professional is an application software used to create E-Books, Digital Magazines, E-Paper and more. 3D PageFlip Professional is a type of flip page software that convert PDF files to page-turning digital publications. Each PDF page can be flipped (back and forth) like a real book. With the PageFlip Professional 3D software you can add videos, images, audio, hyperlinks and multimedia objects [11].

The advantages of this Pageflip Professional 3D media include:

- a. The flip book media can be flipped (back and forth) like a real book. When turning the page, it looks like it is flipping a book, giving rise to a different and more interesting sensation.
- b. In each flip book page an animation is inserted which supports learning material in the form of video or flash animation.

- c. E-book is an interactive learning media in delivering information because it can display multimedia illustrations.

The weaknesses of this app is students tends to tired from reading by looking at the e-book because the monitor will radiate some light that will exhaust some students in long session of reading [12].

The design of handouts using 3D Pageflip Professional explained need to be developed because there are still many feature that need to be tried and used to produce a better and more interesting handouts. It is recommended to install the app to read the results of published 3DP to make it easier to read Handouts that have been created on your computer, the 3D Pageflip Reader application can be installed on the android [13]. Core Stability Materials and Radioactivity in this module is revolving around the Atomic Core. In the Atomic Core we learn two things, Core Energy and Radioactive Energy. While Radioactive learns three things, namely Radiation, Core Activities, and Core Reactions. Of the three material Radioactive Radiation, Core Activities, and Reactions, this Core can be applied in building a Nuclear Reactor. The reason of using the internet to get information such as education because it had 132.7 million internet users consisting of various jobs such as students, students, workers / entrepreneurs, and others. From internet users in Indonesia if separated by occupation, college and students had 7.8% and 6.3% [14]. Therefore, the development of electronic applications is a requirement that should be the current research development [15].

Figure 1. Internet user in Indonesia in 2016

Based on figure 1, we are interested in conducting a study entitled "Designing 3D Pageflip Professional in Core Stability and Radioactivity for high school students." that can be acces anywhere and anytime.

2. Research Methods

In designing the electronic modules, Pageflip must use certain specifications. In making this module, we use computers with this specifications.

Figure 2. The specification of computer that used for making this 3D Pageflip

This study uses research and development. Sugiyono stated that research and development are research methods that used to produce certain products and test the effectiveness of these products [16]. Research activities are conducted to obtain information about user needs (needs assessment) while development activities are carried out to produce research-based learning modules with a scientific approach. The research and development to create this learning website used the development strategy proposed by Thiagarajan. In designing this website, the development steps used are based on 4D with the following stages: Define, Design, Develop, and Dissemination [17].

Phase I *define*, that is the stage of determining and defining the conditions that must be met for the product to be produced. There are five steps that must be done, doing a front and analysis, learner analysis, task analysis, concept analysis and specifying objectives. This step includes initial analysis including reference to the effectiveness of online media, the influence of IT-based learning, analyze the character of students as users, the indicators of learning, and media display strategies that produced. The module media generated already integrate learning components which include: text, images, cover images, videos, animations, formative tests, evaluation questions, and graphic games. As for the software used namely: Microsoft Office Word, Adobe Photoshop CC, Adobe Flash and 3D PageFlip Professional.

Phase II *design*, at this stage an online module based on 3D PageFlip is designed Professional. There are four steps taken in designing an online module based on 3D PageFlip Professional, that is constructing criterion-referenced test, media selection, format selection and initial design. This step includes a study of media quality standards that will generated, the selection of media in accordance with the needs, the selection of display formats selected in accordance with the stated objectives and the initial design of online media based modules 3D PageFlip Professional.

Phase III *develop*, which includes the development of 3D PageFlip based modules is displayed in the form of an electronic module. At this stage it is carried out assessment of the function of all components that are paired according to the intended purpose. This form of module

integrates the display in the form of Microsoft Office Word, Photoshop, Adobe Flash that integrated in the PageFlip software. Also an appropriateness test of the module that displayed in the electronic module.

Phase IV *disseminate*, which is the stage of promoting the products so it can be received by the users. The resulting module is introduced to users, that is students High school. This process is to get responses from users to improve the appearance so that more effective, and efficient in supporting learning.

In making this multimedia-based handout, we uses handout material in the form of core stability and radioactivity material that was previously made using Ms. Word and converted to PDF. In making handout material using Ms. Word needs to pay attention to the following:

1. Font size. After formatted to 3DPageflip application, the display size of the paper will shrink, and if it is made with 12 font size (Normal) the material will looks small in the app.
2. Provide some empty space to insert images, videos, flash and others (if needed).
3. Prepare images, videos, animations, flash, audio and others according to core stability and radioactivity material to complement multimedia-based dynamic fluid handouts.

3. Results and Discussion

Core Stabilization and Radioactivity Handouts are said to be multimedia-based if they include several media in them, for example images, animation, flash, video, audio and other media. Here are some media results that are inserted into the handout with the display on the exe extension. Notice the FIGURE 3.

Figure 3. (a) Book Cover, (b) Flashplayer on E-book, (c) Video animation in one of the page of the E-book, (d) Page view of the E-book

4. Conclusion

This research has produced a learning media in the form of physical digital modules in the core stability and radioactivity material. This generated module is one of the contributions in the development of electronic module learning. This module has been developed by adjusting the stages of the 4D learning model.

The display generated from the electronic module in the Core Stability and Radioactivity material is very interesting and interactive, so it will attract reading interest from readers in the core stability and radioactivity materials. To Access the core stability and radioactivity materials based on multimedia is also very easy because its published to Flash / HTML format that can be opened in any browser. It can be published to other formats such as ZIP, 3DP and EXE.

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“KOMMIKA” MATH AND PHYSICS COMIC APPLICATION AS A LEARNING MEDIA BASED ON ANDROID

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Abstract

Nowadays world is in industry revolution 4.0, it is a condition where technology information has become a base in human's life (Ristekdikti, 2018). One of development in industry is utilization comic as entertainment media visual by use gadget. Indonesian comic books association (AKSI) noted that 13 million people read Indonesian comics by their smartphone (Harian Nasional, 2018). However, the contents of these comics are still dominated with entertainment and few comics has educational content. Based on the result of preliminary research, we found that 95,7% students enjoy learning by using android application, 56,5% students stated that an alternative of learning media is the usage of android application, 78,3% students are interested in using android application as a learning media, and 73,9% students agreed to use android media as their learning media. On the other hand, based on the research, the most difficult lesson according to the student is math and physics. To compensate for these conditions, KOMMIKA (Komik Matematika dan Fisika) is created as a learning media based on android application which also contains knowledge of science linked to everyday life. KOMMIKA is a visual learning media based on android to minimize the challenges that students face when learning mathematics and physics.

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1. Introduction

Science has an important role in supporting human's life. Mathematics and physics are the branches of science which are often learned. These two lessons are related to each other. Many mathematical concepts used as physics solving techniques, such as vector calculation, speed, thermodynamics and others.

Mathematics and physics are a very important lessons to be taught to the student. In Indonesia, this is indicated by the existence of mathematics and physics lesson since elementary school. Physics that are learned in science lesson teach students how to understand physical phenomena in this world. In physics lesson student learn why the sun rises in the east, why is there day and night, why do things fall down when it thrown, why is there changes of objects after burning, and many more.

Such problems can be answered using a physical and mathematical approach. However, there are problems such as learning methods or media that are still conventional and often inhibit student in understanding these lessons. In mathematics, problems that often arise are students' reasoning ability, skills and understanding of teachers in carrying out learning process, students' awareness of learning, student with memory, language, or reasoning disorders, and feeling of fear from the student [1]. In Physics, in general the problem that arise are due to students' weakness in structured abilities especially the ability to use knowledge schemes in create problem solving strategies, misconception, mathematical abilities, and the ability to understand prerequisite knowledge.

Nowadays, world is in industrial revolution 4.0, that is the condition has been become a base in human's life. The development of the massive internet and digital technology makes things borderless with computing and unlimited data [2]. In the presence of industrial revolution 4.0, we need to use technology to solve problems in learning.

One of the solutions to overcome the problems in learning is using visual media in giving teaching to mathematics and physics lesson. Based on the results of research by Widyasari [3] that the gift of visual props in physics learning is more effective than without visual props. Many teenagers are currently using pictorial media like as Webtoon or Instagram.

Webtoon users in August 2017 reached over 6 million users [4]. Instagram besides being a place to upload personal photos, is now a comic platform like as shenscomics, tahilalats, Si Juki, and others. In July 2017, Instagram user reached 45 million users [5]. It shows that teenagers are now likely to use media pictorial in their days. After looking at this situation, the issue of mathematics and physics learning can be solved by using media pictorial in its learning, not only through conventional text books. For that, we innovate created an android app called KOMMIKA (Comic Math and Physics based on Digital Apps). KOMMIKA.NET is a digital-based visual learning media that is carefully packed with purpose of facilitating student in learning mathematics and physics lesson to improve student knowledge with the approach of daily life issues. Characters and storyline of the comic in KOMMIKA refers to understanding of the concept of mathematics and physics.

Tedjasaputra argues that comics are illustrated cartoon stories where the elements of the picture are more important than the story [6]. According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary, comics are illustrated stories (in a magazine, newspaper, or in the form of books) which are generally easy to digest and funny [7]. Handayani stated that "comic is a visual communication media that has the power to convey information popularly and easily understood [8]. Based on the above opinions it can be concluded that comics are visual communication media in the form of illustrated cartoon stories that are generally easy to digest and funny and have the power to convey information in a popular and easy to understand manner.

Adi in Agatha explained the types of comics into several types, namely: cartoon/cartoon (cartoon), comic strip, comic book, comic annual, comic album, online comic, instructional book in comic format, series of illustrations (Storyboard), comic bookings (simple comic), and comic planning thoughts. However, the type of comic that will be developed is online comics [9].

According to Gagne in Barus and Suratno media are various types of components in the student environment that can stimulate them to study [10]. Whereas according to Briggs in Barus and Suratno media are all physical devices that can present messages stimulating students to study [11]. Barus and Suratno said that the media is a tool used in the teaching and learning process aims to facilitate the teacher in conveying the subject matter and make it easier for students to absorb, understand or master the subject matter they receive [12]. Based on the above opinion it can be concluded that the media is a physical tool in the student environment that is used for teaching and learning processes that can present messages in a way that stimulates students to learn so as to make it easier for teachers to convey the subject matter and facilitate students in absorbing, understanding or mastering the material he received .

According to the Large Dictionary, Indonesian visual language is something that can be seen with the sight (eye) [13]. Prihadi suggested that visual is a learning activity by observing and describing [14]. Royan suggested that visuals are people who prefer to use vision in receiving information [15]. Based on the above opinion it can be concluded that visual is an activity of learning or receiving information through vision by observing and describing something that can be seen with the sense of vision.

Visual media can be interpreted as a physical tool in the student environment that is used for teaching and learning processes that can present messages by stimulating students through vision

to learn by observing and describing something that can be seen by the visual senses making it easier for the teacher to convey the subject matter and facilitate students in absorbing, understanding or mastering the material they receive.

Duffy and Roehler in Lefudin suggested that learning is a system that aims to help the student learning process, which contains a series of events that are designed, arranged in such a way as to influence and support the occurrence student learning processes that are internal [16]. According to Sudjana in Darma, learning is every effort made intentionally by educators that causes participants to carry out learning activities [17]. Miarso in Siregar et al. Stated that learning is an educational effort that is carried out intentionally, with the objectives set before the process is carried out, and its implementation is controlled [18]. So, learning is an educational effort that is done intentionally with a predetermined goal to help students' learning processes that are designed and structured in such a way that it can support the occurrence of an internal learning process.

Eggen and Kauchak in Lefudin explained that there are six characteristics of effective learning, namely (1) students become active reviewers of the environment through observing, comparing, finding similarities and differences and forming concepts and generalizations based on similarities found, (2) the teacher provides material as focused thinking and interacting in the lesson, (3) student activities are fully based on assessment, (4) the teacher is actively involved in providing direction and guidance to students in analyzing information, (5) learning orientation of content mastery lessons and development of thinking skills, and (6) teachers use varied teaching techniques according to the goals and style of teacher teaching [19].

2. Objectives

KOMMIKA (Komik Matematika dan Fisika) is created as a learning media based on android application which also contains knowledge of science linked to everyday life. KOMMIKA is a visual learning media based on android to minimize the challenges that students face when learning mathematics and physics. This study was conducted for 8 month januari to August 2018 which focused on the design and program of the media at the Secretariat of the Young Research Group of the Jakarta State University. The method used in designing this application is type system development method waterfall. This method was chosen because the stages are systematic and easy to apply. This research method will be presented in a flow chart image. the existing steps can be seen in figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart

Need analysis is used to get information, models, specifications about the software that the client / user wants. Both parties between the client and the software maker are actively involved in this stage. The system design stage allocates system requirements both hardware and software with a variety of system architectures as a whole. Software design and depiction of basic system software and intelligence abstraction. At this stage of implementation, software design is realized as a series of programs or program units. Testing involves verifying that each unit meets its specifications. In the testing phase, individual units of programs or programs are combined and tested as a complete system to ascertain whether or not they meet the needs of the software. After testing, the software can be sent to the user. Testing is done by blackbox testing and counting with statistics Descriptive. One of the results of the descriptive analysis will bring up calculations that are valued between 0 to 10. The average calculation is then interpreted according to the following interval:

Table 1 Statistics Descriptive

Average value interval	Interpretation
$0 < \text{mean} < 3,3$	the application runs poorly
$3,4 < \text{mean} < 6,6$	the application runs pretty well
$6,7 < \text{mean} < 10$	the application runs very well

3. Result and Discussion

The research method used in the study uses the Waterfall, the first stage carried out in this method is the needs analysis in which the problem can be inferred from the interviewee. The resource person here is the sample that is the target of marketing. The results of the needs analysis showed that 95,7% students enjoy learning by using android application, 56,5% students stated that an alternative of learning media is the usage of android application, 78,3% students are interested in using android application as a learning media, and 73,9% students agreed to use android media

as their learning media from the problem already identified, then design is done for help development system. Problems that arise I will make the features the available in the application this. There are designs for this application.

Figure 2. Design Of User Interaction With The System

This application was created by using Android Studio software. This software was chosen because of it provides a lot of libraries which can make it easier making Android applications. Where as for making web, researchers use Codeigniter framework. Framework is framework in engineering codings so functions frequent programming it is not written again like equivalent form, login handling, base access data, and others. Codeigniter chosen because it's simple, MVC concept (Model View Controller), has a level security, its users many, and have tools elegant. Management database created using phpMyAdmin. The programming language the one used is PHP, Javascript, HTML, and Bootstrap. designing and build this application, needed some software that is AndroidStudio, Ganymotion, Sublime Text and Web Browser. Android Studio is used to build

Android based application. this software too provides a lot of libraries that can be used that can facilitate system development. Ganymotion is used as an Android or an application can run an Android program in the Windows operating system. Sublime Text is used as an editor PHP. Web programming language the browser is used for display HTML and PHP code.

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Figure 3. Display android studio work to create applications.

The Kommika Android application can be used for users with Android software with a minimum version of 2.3.5 (Gingerbread).

ii. Product Development

The media manufacturing stage is the realization stage of the system design, at this stage learning media is created using Android Studio and Corel Draw. use of corel draw for the manufacture of comic designs and user interfaces, corel draw is used because it can produce images in the form of HD which makes the user more comfortable with the appearance of the application while the android studio software is used for programming applications so that they can be used by the user. Android studio is used because there is a library that facilitates coding of android programs

Figure 4. Main View 2

Figure 5. Login Page

On the main display page there is information and general objectives of KOMMIKA that are intended for each user. This is so that users can understand first about KOMMIKA and its objectives before using the application.

Login Page is one of the main pages at KOMMIKA, on this page users are required to have an account in order to access KOMMIKA wherever and whenever. Users who do not have an account will be asked to create me by signing up and filling in the personal data including name, e-mail address, and password to be able to register. Users who have registered for meals will be able to log in by entering their e-mail and password

Figure 6. Home Page 1

Figure 7. Quiz

On the home page, there are various choices of facilities that can be used by users freely. Available facilities include math comics, physics comics, material summaries, and quizzes. On this page there is also information about the favorite comic titles telling users and information about the top comics based on the number of readers.

Quiz page is intended for users who want to know the level of their understanding of the mathematical and physical concepts that have been obtained previously through comics and material summaries. On this page there is a score that provides information that the user's answer is right or wrong

Figure 8. List Of Comic

Figure 9. Example Comic

Comics are the main facilities found in KOMMIKA, there are 2 choices of material offered, namely mathematics and physics where in each material there are various titles that users can access freely. The storyline in the comics found in KOMMIKA is based on local culture and everyday life related to mathematics and physics, so readers can easily understand the basic concepts of physics and mathematics. Testing of the KOMMIKA.NET application is done using black box testing. The instrument and the testing results are as follows:

Table 2. Blackbox Testing Result

No.	Feature/action	expected results	test results
1	Register/sign up	after users input their data like name, school, born date, etc., then clicking 'Daftar' (Register), the data is stored in the database.	1
2	login to the server	After users input username and password, the apps shown its main page.	1
3	choose the subject categories	The list of comics appear.	1
4	choose the comic title	The comic appears according to what user has choosen.	1
5	click the 'like' button	The apps stores data into SQLite.	0
Total			4
Percentage			80%

Based on the table , it is found that most of the feature in this application can already be used with an 80% success rate. It shows that all function can be used properly.

4. Conclusion

The problem raised in the writing of this research is how to design and build KOMMIKA applications as visual media for learning Mathematics and Physics. The system development method used is methodology that consists of requirements gathering, planning, coding, and testing. The results of the development of this system is the creation of an KOMMIKA application based on Android with features such as class selection, reading, enjoying, and viewing subtitles. Stages of application starts from problem identification, design making base with phpMyAdmin, making interface display with Android Studio help, and creating logical business using Java programming language. After testing with the blackboxtesting method, the KOMMIKA application can be used by its functions with a success rate of 80%.

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ANDALUS (BERANDA PEMUDA MUSLIM) AS AN ANDROID APPLICATION BASED LEARNING MEDIA ON STUDY AL-QUR'AN FOR MILLENNIAL GENERATION

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Abstract

Islam guarantees life for every adherent in the world and in the hereafter and Islam has a very essential joint of the Qur'an. Samsul Nizar (2002) says Islamic education is a series of systematic, planned and comprehensive process in an effort to transfer the values to the students, develop the potential of the students, so that students are able to carry out their duties on earth as best as possible all dimensions of life. The millennial issue of Muslims is now very worrisome because they started away with their Qur'an, do not want to learn Arabic which is the language to understand the Qur'an and more closely with its gadgets. Arsyad (2017) says the visual media can attract and direct people's attention to concentrate on the content of an information, in which case the visual source can inspire one's emotions and attitudes so as to speed up the process of understanding and remembering messages. Based on that statement, the right solution in helping millennials in the process of understanding the Qur'an is by developing a translation application of the Qur'anic Tafsir Ibnu Katsir with an audio and visual display called ANDALUS. ANDALUS is a medium of information, and an android based communication to welcome the industrial revolution 4.0 to the millennium to get closer to the Qur'an. This research uses research and development method. The results of this study show a high appreciation because the millennials consider the translation of the Qur'an more easily understood and easy to remember. In addition, this application also contains all the verses of the Qur'an so that the millennial more understand the contents of the Qur'an universally.

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1. Introduction

Islamic education guarantees life for every adherent in the world and hereafter. Islamic education has very essential joints, namely the Qur'an and Sunnah. It contains basic teachings (basic principles) concerning all aspects of human life, which then can be developed according to the reason of each nation, whenever the time, and wherever it is, Islam is always present functionally solving humanitarian problems, because everything is contained in it [1]. Samsul Nizar (2002) writes in his book, Islamic education is a series of systematic, planned and comprehensive processes in an effort to transfer values to students, developing the potential that exists in students, so that students are able to carry out their duties on the earth as well as in all dimensions of life. The problem of the current Muslim millennial is very worrying because they start far away with the Qur'an, do not want to learn Arabic which is a language to understand Al-Quran and get closer to the gadget. The rapid growth of the internet is one of the reasons for this.

The Internet has touched and changed almost the human life side, reached 3 million Internet users in the world in 2016 [2]. Predictions from Google Executive Chairman Eric Schmidt mention that by 2020 all the world's populations are connected to the Internet. The International

Telecommunication Union (ITU) reports that 80% of teenagers (15-24) in 104 countries are online using Mobile Smartphones [3]. The number of Smartphone usage in Quarter 3rd 2016 worldwide has touched 7.5 billion, specifically for comparison market shares operating system (OS) is controlled by Android 65%, and the rest by IOS, Windows Phone, and Blackberry [4]. Smartphones in Indonesia now reach about 25% of the total population or about 90 million people and increase 6 million per year [5]. Indonesia is going digital with 261 million population around 13,700 islands, 33 provinces, over 500 districts with roughly 58 million learners, 3 million teachers, and 302,097 schools [6].

In general, the challenge of education in Indonesia is a high priority to increase learners' interest in learning, improving teacher quality, increasing efficiency, and effectiveness of media based learning [7]. Khaeruddin Said (2018) have published a research Development of Media-Based Learning using Android Mobile Learning that the conclusion of his paper can be taken based on data of research result and discussion of android application development as learning media is very decent. The delivery of information and learning materials to the learner's from teachers is more interactive, involving more contact, communication and collaboration with people easily, inexpensively and accessibility anywhere and anytime. Comparison with other digital learning media such as using desktop-based/notebook-based multimedia is quite troublesome, expensive and immobile for the learner [8].

Arsyad said visual media can attract and direct people's attention to concentrate on the contents of an information. In this case visual sources can arouse a person's emotions and attitudes so that they can speed up the process of understanding and remembering messages. According to the Education and Communication Technology Association in America, media are all forms and channels that people use to send messages or information. The National Education Association has a different understanding of media, they define media as forms of both printed and audiovisual communication and equipment. The media can be used to send messages from the sender to the recipient so that it can stimulate students' thoughts, feelings, attention and interests in such a way that the learning process occurs [9].

Mobile Learning very helpful for students in understanding learning. Muhammad Hassan Massaty (2017) make an application call Sekar Indonesia. Sekar Indonesia had been tested its performance and its feasibility. From the performance test was known all function worked properly for each smarthphone with different specification. The result of feasibility test of Sekar Indonesia learning media is done by material experts, media experts and users. The average of the overall aspects of the feasibility of materials experts, media experts and users is 86.1%, 92.85% and 98%. From these results indicate that the application of Sekar Indonesia is very appropriate to serve as a companion learning media for students [10].

We have shown how an agent can extract information from an audio-visual content following a theoretical formulation based on the Channel Theory. After showing it, we have established a possible method of representation of all the informative values that an agent can obtain from a content using a matrix formed by the channels the agent is able to establish on the content. Finally, we have exposed how this representation allows us to illustrate the evolution of informative items through the evolution of audio-visual content. The next objective of this research is to assess how the variations of the information matrix can allow the obtaining by the agent of new classifications and channels that go beyond the objects represented in the content, and also can allow an approach to the understanding of the semantic and syntactic levels of content by the agent [11].

Receiving information from different senses is highly advantageous since events become more salient which in turn enables quicker and more adequate responses to crossmodal compared to unimodal stimuli [12]. Despite a huge body of research the question of how the brain combines information from the different senses into a coherent percept is still not fully understood. It has been suggested that so-called supramodal features, that is, features which are redundantly coded

by multiple sensory systems, are used to judge whether or not inputs from different modalities originate from the same source. Examples of supramodal features are time, space, number and meaning⁴: the higher the overlap of inputs from different sensory modalities with regard to supramodal features, the more likely the brain will treat these inputs as coming from the same source. For example, a bouncing ball makes a sound each time the ball hits the ground and both sound and visual motion appear at the same location. Hence it is likely to perceive one object producing both types of sensory input [13].

Roger Bergh (2015) The information base solution will support teachers, instructors, Small and Medium Sized Enterprises with training methods promoting pedagogical use of audio and video technology into instructional processes. The new training principles aim to facilitate this integration through the dissemination of information on good practices and the fostering of a community of peers for the sharing of information and experiences, both technical and pedagogical. The new audio-visual information base services, to be completed in the fall of 2007, offer the European educational society model recommendations for pedagogical use, as well as adaptation and effective integration of audio-visual communication and collaboration services for transfer of training, competence and knowledge to Small and Medium Sized Enterprises (SME). The services aim at the creation and fostering of a community within distance education for the sharing of information related to the integration of audio and video technology within pedagogical methodologies [14].

M. Alqahtani and A. Fayyumi (2015) Technology in the educational process is not new and mobile learning applications are becoming more pervasive. Therefore, it is very necessary to understand their impact if being used in learning options. Nowadays, great efforts are being made to develop speech recognition applications for mobile devices. It helps the user to interact with the device as if he was speaking to another person. Arabic speech recognition has its challenging characteristics and many researchers have performed studies regarding them. One of them is how to recognize verbal Quran verses. This study focuses on developing the Say Quran Android application and then studying the attitudes of students toward this application. This work can be improved and more work can be done to add modifications and additional features. The current version of the software supports only a few languages but more languages can be added in the future work. More importantly, an in-depth study of the impact of such an application on students' learning should be conducted [15].

Yapeng Tian (2018) makes research In this work, we study a suit of five research questions in the context of three audio-visual event localization tasks. We propose both baselines and novel algorithms to address each of the three tasks. Our systematic study also supports our findings: modeling jointly over auditory and visual modalities outperforms independent modeling, audio-visual event localization in a noisy condition is still tractable, the audio-guided visual attention is able to capture semantic regions of sound sources and can even distinguish audio-visual unrelated videos, temporal alignments are important for audio-visual feature fusion, the proposed dual residual network is capable of audio-visual fusion, and strong correlations existing between the two modalities enable cross-modality localization [16].

So, the right solution to help millennials in the process of getting closer to the Koran is by developing an Al-Quran translation media with audio and visual appearance. A concrete solution that can be applied is to develop an application called ANDALUS (Beranda Pemuda Muslim). ANDALUS is an Android-based learning, information and communication media to welcome the industrial revolution 4.0 to the millennials to get closer to the Qur'an.

2. Objectives

The purpose of this research is to produce Android-based learning media, information, and communication devices in the form of Al-Quran translation media with audio and visual display.

The benefit of making this media is to help Muslim youth be able to carry out their duties on the earth as well as possible in all dimensions of life.

3. Methodology

3.1. Place and Time of Research

This study was conducted for two months from July to August 2018 which focused on the design of the media at the Secretariat of the Young Research Group of the Jakarta State University.

3.2. Research Stages

The research begins with conducting a needs analysis using user analysis questionnaire techniques. The research process continued on the feasibility test by the expert team in terms of material and media using interview techniques. The resulting product was tested to users in small groups using a questionnaire.

3.3. Research Methods

The research method used in the study uses the Research and Development method. According to Sugiyono, Method of Research and Development or research development is a research method used to produce certain products, and test the effectiveness of these products. The development method adapts from the ADDIE development model developed by Dick and Carry to design learning media. The development model consists of five stages which include analysis (analysis), design (design), development (implementation), and implementation (evaluation).

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Product Development Results

4.1.1. Product Needs Analysis

The research method used in the study uses the Research and Development method. According to Sugiyono, Method of Research and Development or research development is a research method used to produce certain products, and test the effectiveness of these products. The development method adapts from the ADDIE development model developed by Dick and Carry to design learning media. The development model consists of five stages which include analysis (analysis), design (design), development (implementation), and implementation (evaluation).

The results of the needs analysis showed that 58.1% of respondents did not understand what he was reading from the Koran, 74.4% of respondents tried to read the translations of the Koran to understand the content of the Koran and the rest varied, some by listening to studies and some by asking. In addition, 90.7% said they all had the Al-Quran application on their smartphones. And unfortunately they only read the translation without knowing the interpretation that is more or less possible different from the meaning of the verse. Also the data shows that they feel comfortable every day with a short video display that contains audio at the same time as visual, they feel more focused when seeing it which is around 89.5%. So from that analysis we direct if the Qur'anic interpretation application is made with their audio visual form, they answer 82.6% agree and like it.

4.1.2. Media Making Design

The media manufacturing stage is the realization stage of the flowchart design, at this stage learning media is created using Android Studio, Corel Draw, and Wondershare Filmora software.

Steps for Making an Application using Corel Draw: The first step is to open the Corel Draw worksheet for the new clinics in the window and select a custom paper worksheet with a full 1000 pt x 1000 pt.

The appearance made guided by the interpretation of Ibn Katsir which is the most widely known book of interpretation. Then a visual appearance is made using corel draw with a phrase quotation according to the interpretation of Ibn Katsir. After the display is made, the audio is added with voice dubbing and combined using the Wondershare Filmora application. Lastly, the phrase quotations quran are uploaded to the android application according to the flowchart in Figure 1.

After the content is ready, then coding is done on the Android application by using the Android Studio application by referring to the flowchart that has been created. Display of Android studio worksheets as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Application flowchart to be created

Figure 2. Display Android studio work to create applications

Android apps that have been filled with Quran content can be accessed using a smartphone with a minimum of Android 5.0 specifications.

4.1.3. Product Development

The media manufacturing stage is the realization stage of the flowchart design, at this stage learning media is created using Android Studio, Corel Draw, and Wondershare Filmora software.

Figure 1. Picture of the Andalus Application

Figure 2. Selected Mail Menu Options

Figure 3. Surat View

4.2. Research result

In this study, the researcher carried out the stages, namely taking data to media experts and material experts using Likert scale questionnaires and interviews as well as questionnaires to usability tests for users in small groups.

4.2.1. Media Expert Validation Results

Based on the results of interviews obtained from media experts, His name is Med Irzal, M.Kom lecturers of the UNJ Computer Science study program, stated that the appearance of colors, images and audio is good enough. However, the appearance of the application is like a normal website. In addition, structure and navigation are not consistent and difficult to understand. So, the application must be repaired again.

4.2.2. Expert Validation Results Material

After making improvements to it, the research application validated the material experts, her name is Dian Nurohmah alumni of the Sukoharjo Al-Uthuwah Islamic Boarding School and also the teaching staff at the As As Sakinah Youth Study Salman Al - Farisi Rawamangun Mosque. The result of the interview that the content of the application is good. Audio visuals are also quite supportive in the process of understanding the Qur'anic interpretation. However, foreign words that are difficult to understand by ordinary people should be eliminated. In order not to cause mistreatment. after validation is carried out immediately revised according to the direction of experts. after the revision was done, the researcher conducted a usability test.

4.2.3. Usability Test Results

Jako Nielsen stated that for usability test, it was enough with only 5 respondents, because in testing the users who were the focus was the site's functionality to see which design elements were easy and which were difficult to use. Evaluating the quality of design elements does not depend on how many people use the application. Therefore, the researcher decided to spread the questionnaire to only 5 respondents.

The measurement technique used is using a Likert scale. For the purposes of quantitative analysis, answers are given a predetermined score of one, two, three, four and five.

Table 1. The Likert Scale

NO	Kategori	Skor
1	Very good	5
2	Good	4
3	Enough	3
4	Less	2
5	Very Less	1

The percentage of eligibility is calculated using the formula:

$$\% = \frac{\text{Number of Answer Scores}}{\text{The Maximum Total Score of Each Indicator}} \times 100\%$$

If the value of the percentage of feasibility has been obtained then the next is the appointment of the quality predicate of the product made based on the Rating Scale measurement scale. The scale of the Rating Scale designation is the conversion of qualitative to quantitative data. With the Rating Scale the raw data obtained in the form of numbers is then interpreted in a qualitative sense. The following table is the Rating Scale used to determine the feasibility of the product:

Table 2. Rating Scale

NO	Score in percent (%)	Feasibility Category
1	0 - 25%	very unfit
2	>25% - 27%	not feasible
3	>50% - 75%	Worthy
4	>75% - 100%	Very decent

The results of our research questionnaire are as follows figure 3.

Figure 3. Usability Test Result

Based on the diagram above, the efficiency indicator has a percentage of 82.86% or included in the very feasible category. Meanwhile, for the display has a percentage of 84% or belongs to a very decent category. Then, for interactivity has a percentage of 78.86% or belongs to a very feasible category. The average of the three indicators is 81.9% or it can be said that the usability level of this application is very decent.

5. Conclusion

Based on the research, it can be concluded that, based on the validity test of the Andalus application media experts, the structure and navigation must be improved to be more systematic and consistent. Meanwhile, evaluations from material experts, namely the content delivered must use language that is easily understood by ordinary people. The Andalus application has a very reasonable usability level. The conclusion was taken from the three indicators, namely efficiency, appearance and interactivity, with values of 82.86%, 84%, 78.86%, while for the average value of the three indicators, 81.9%. The results of this study show a high appreciation because the millennials consider the translation of the Qur'an more easily understood and easy to remember. In addition, this application also contains all the verses of the Qur'an so that the millennial more understand the contents of the Qur'an universally.

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THE LEADERSHIP OF MADRASAH PRINCIPALS IN IMPROVING LEARNING QUALITY AT MADRASAH TSANAWIYAH NEGERI KOTO DIAN KECAMATAN KELILING DANAU KABUPATEN KERINCI

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Abstract

This study took place in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci Regency. Selection of this setting was based on the consideration of Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci regency where it is one of the Madrasahs that has many limitations affected the management of the school as a whole. So the researcher rose the main issue of the study. To know how the pattern of leadership on the head of madrasah in improving the quality of learning in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci regency. To know factors influencing leadership of madrasah head in improving quality of learning at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci Regency. To find out what efforts made by Madrasah Principals in improving the quality of learning in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci.

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1. Introduction

The research method used to study the leadership of madrasah principals in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci Regency was a qualitative method. Based on the problems faced, this was studied by using an educational perspective, with a descriptive analytical approach supported by data obtained from literatures and documents related to the problems studied. Data collection was carried out by researcher to get information of desired data, in this case researcher used instruments; interview, observation, and documentation. Data analysis used in this research was data flow analysis model. According to Miles and Huberman (year), principle data analysis activity is during the research activity (during data collection), and the most core activities include data deduction (data reduction), data presentation (display data) as well as drawing conclusions (making conclusion), observation/ persistence, triangulation techniques, and consultation mentors. The implications of this study were: 1) the principal needs support by all parties, both consistent principals to realize the achieving school and the quality of the students themselves as well as adequate facilities and infrastructure, 2) the existence of learning facilities for teachers can not be eliminated, the learning facilities is useful to help teachers conduct learning activities effectively and efficiently, 3) three factors that must exist and greatly determine the educational and learning activities; teachers, students, and learning instruments. The absence of any of these factors can affect the educational and learning process.

2. Discussion

The head of the madrasah is the person responsible for the achievement of the school's objectives, especially in relation to the quality of education as well as the customer satisfaction of the teachers

internally and the parents of the students externally. In order to obtain quality and customer satisfaction, the principal should have a friendly attitude and open to subordinates. The principal also means a profession that demands the mastery of a number of abilities and competencies. Thus, the person appointed to be the principal must firstly obtain educational **prajabatan** earlier. According to Mulyono (year) cited by Wahab and Umiarso (year), the principal of madrasah should have some requirements to create madrasah that they lead to be an effective madrasah such as have good physical and spiritual health, sticking to the goals achieved, excited, proficient in giving guidance, honest, smart and competent in terms of teaching and paying good attention and striving to achieve it. Apart from these requirements, the Regulation of the Minister of National Education of Indonesian Republic number 13 of 2007 on principal standards of Madrasah also states about the competencies that must be owned by the Principal of Madrasah; personality, managerial, entrepreneurship, supervision, and social. The quality of madrasah in general can be seen from several aspects; 1) formulation of vision, mission and goals, 2) teacher competence and other human resources, 3) development of the curriculum, 4) effectiveness of teaching and learning process, 5) relevance of facilities and infrastructure, 6) accuracy of evaluation, and 7) quality of input and output of learners. Quality assurance of formal, nonformal and informal education as written in the regulation of the Minister of National Education number 63 in 2009 on the quality assurance system of education, is a systematic and integrated activities in the implementation of education to improve the nation's intelligence life. Systematic and integrated activities are carried out by educational units, the implementation of educational units, local government, government, and the community as well as involving the business world. Based on the observations that the researchers did, the principal should be able to guide, organize, influence, mobilize, and coordinate the implementation of educational tasks in improving the quality of learning. The indication showed that leadership pattern in Madrasah was not yet fully run, there were still teachers who had not been able to properly analyze the subject matter, and learners can not compete with other schools. Based on the previous discussion, then in this section, the researchers pointed out several points as a result of the main problem analysis, research objectives, theory exposure and research results. The conclusions can be described as follows.

1. Leadership Pattern on Head of Madrasah in MTSN Koto Dian Kerinci Regency

In implementing the rules and regulations in Madrasah, the head of the madrasah as the top leader applies a democratic and participative leadership model. Where in implementing the order, the head of the madrasah always refers to the rules that have been mutually agreed upon. In implementing the leadership functions, the head of Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci regency is more dominant in implementing the function of equating the shared vision of empowering the members through cooperative working team, giving examples and awakening the soul to continuously improve technical skills and interpersonal skills. Thus, supervision is the success of the management process. Therefore, supervision needs to be viewed comprehensively, because this oversight function is the answer between planning and procurement and also the implementation, maintenance, and mining of the management process. The results of interviews with the head of madrasah and staff of MTSN Koto Dian Kerinci regency on the leadership patterns of madrasah heads in improving the quality of learning, it is correct but not quite right, because according to the theory expressed by Mulyasa that the head of a successful school should be able to develop management and leadership and understand the full vision of his school.

2. Factors Influencing the Head Leadership of Madrasah in Improving the Quality of Learning at MTSN Koto Dian Kerinci Regency

Factors that constrain the head of the madrasah in improving teacher discipline lead to two main issues; social sensitivity and the influence of local culture, in addition with the factor of educational financing.

a. Internal and External Factors

In the process of education and teaching in a school can be influenced by internal factors and external Factors for both the head of Madrasah, teachers and students at MtsN Koto Dian Kerinci regency. Those factors can be inadequate facilities and infrastructure, concerning the quality of teachers, curriculum, teaching and learning process, and other supporting facilities such as administrative staff and libraries which are all one system in the context of the transfer process of teaching, so those factors are not located on the results. If these factors are met well and have quality then in turn will produce and improve the quality of education in schools. This illustrates that a head of madrasah should be responsible for all madrasah development plans, have clear objectives, manage finances, oversee learning programs, and prepare planning reports. Thus, the head of the madrasah as a manager in the organization of the madrasah should be the pattern of leadership improved in such a way as to improve the quality of learning in the madrasah.

3. Efforts Made by the Head of Madrasah in Improving the Quality of Learning in MTSN Koto Dian Kerinci Regency

The efforts made by the head of the madrasah in improving the discipline of teachers are be *tauladan* for all elements of madrasah in terms of obeying the rules and regulations of madrasah, imposing daily attendance, and having interpersonal approach to teachers. Based on the observation and interviews data with principals and some teachers, it can be understood that the efforts of the principal in managing facilities and infrastructure to improve the quality of learning in MtsN Koto Dian Kerinci Regency is good and right, although there are factors that affect in the realization while the leadership of the principal of MtsN Koto Dian of Kerinci Regency in managing the school should be appreciated only how the principal is fully responsible for the maintenance of facilities and infrastructure in the school, with always maintained so as not to be easily damaged and still able to be used with the best.

Additionally, based on the observation and interviews with the head of madrasah and some teachers, it can be concluded that the efforts of the head madrasah in improving the quality of learning in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci, there has been an effort from the principal to overcome and improve leadership in improving the quality of learning in madrasah. That is the head of Madrasahs creates the quality of the learning experience. This aims to improve the quality of education in order to become more qualified. Improving the quality of learning with an interpersonal approach model is a psychological effort in providing understanding to teachers and administrative personnel in terms of how to create a good madrasah environment.

Implications

The implications expressed in this section refer to the conclusions mention earlier are the leadership of the madrasah head is still weak and needs revamping in the future to revise more realistic teacher discipline improvement program. To achieve achievement educational institutions, the educational institutions need to have good administrative management education. These activities involve all the arrangement activities or arrangements to establish a group of people to achieve goals such as teachers and employees. In relation to that, the teaching administration being the head of the madrasah's assessment includes the annual program learning plan, the semester program, the teaching preparation, the improvement program and the enrichment. Some of these aspects become the main priority concept of madrasah head in assessing teacher discipline. Furthermore, the head of the madrasah has not been able to work on

planning, organizing activities, directing, coordinating and conducting supervision, evaluating activities, determining policies, holding meetings, making decisions and organizing learning processes to achieve organizational goals, while he has not been able to empower all resources communities and the environment that aims to educate the life of the nation, including its responsibility in the distribution of teachers in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci regency. Leadership of madrasah head in improving the quality of learning needs to arrange in general all aspects of madrasah that have a link with the teacher, so that teachers can work professionally and competence maximally as supervision of teacher discipline. Absolute supervision should be carried out by the head of the madrasah considering the function of the head as a supervisor, the head of the madrasah must supervise the class at least twice in one semester. In fact, the head of a madrasah only adopts a policy of delegating supervisory duties to the deputy head of the madrasah in the curriculum field, or a senior teacher who has the competence in supervision. If the head of the madrasah has no opportunity to carry it out by himself, the supervision of the class carried out by the head of madrasah can not run properly, it shows the weakness of leadership, especially in the field of supervision both conducted by the local department of education and internal supervision conducted by the head of madrasah.

The leadership of madrasah head in upbringing has close links and needs to be synchronized in aligning the attainment of the more realistic educational objectives of Madrasah Tsanawiyah Madrasah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci. In planning the teacher discipline evaluation program, the head of the madrasah also establishes short-term goals, medium-term assessments, and long-term assessments. In the short-term preferred assessment, the most important is the factor of teacher presence, *istiqamah*, and discipline. Medium-term assessments focus on teacher quality and classroom supervision, and on long-term assessments focus on the totality of teacher quality improvement, professional evaluation, and teacher mapping. Based on data from several opinions and search results in the field of research, the researchers conclude that the coaching of extracurricular activities becomes a necessity in improving discipline in the madrasah environment, especially in personal discipline of each teacher in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci regency. Because with the formation of teachers, it will motivate students to always follow in complying with all rules established together. This condition is one of important points for madrasah head in disciplinary development at the madrasah, with the policy of the headmaster in giving responsibility to the teacher to guide the students in carrying out extracurricular activities into concrete steps in shaping and cultivating discipline, especially among teachers. In viewing the success or failure of disciplinary coaching, it can be seen from the end of the guidance conducted by the teacher, whether the students built the progress as expected, or even declined. Overall, teachers are one of the determinants of success or failure of an education because education will be responsible for the personal formation of students. Thus, the administrative management of teachers in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci regency aimed towards increasing the quality of madrasah. The head of a professional democratic madrasah through professional appointments also helps this process. This will foster a democratic climate in madrasah, which will encourage a conducive climate for the creation of optimal learning quality to develop the potential of learners. The head of a madrasah is a person who is really expected to be a leader. Therefore, the leadership quality of madrasah head determines good and bad management of personnel administration (teacher). Teacher management requires highly independent and professional madrasah heads with strong administrative skills, in order to be able to take decisions and initiatives to improve the quality of madrasah.

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INTERLOCKING BETWEEN TRADITIONAL CUSTODY AND LEMBAGO OF JAMBI MALAY: STUDY OF MEANING

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Abstract

Interlocking between Traditional Custody and Lembago of Jambi Malay is one of the traditions in the custom of Malay Jambi marriage. This tradition is a traditional event that has been passed down through generations in the form of Seloko Adat, which is full of the meaning of life that needs to be preserved. Therefore, the aim of the research is expressing the meanings which are contained in it. The method used in this research is qualitative descriptive with content and hermeneutic analysis approach and to obtain the validity of the data used triangulation. The Result of the research are 1. Kato Bajawab in front of the house between the elders or spokesman from the bride and the groom, 2. Continuing to the ballroom, the event is starting with 1) read the Al-Quran, 2) eating betel leaves and smoking cigarettes, 3) the parents of the groom gave something to the bride, 4) the elders of the bride and groom checked and received delivery, 5) the grandmothers of both parties asked for an order or opinion from the mediators, 6) customary procession accepted by all parties, 7) determination of marriage day, 8) prayer reading, and 9) informal conversation. From the results of the research, the meaning contained in seloko Interlocking between Traditional Custody and Lembago of Jambi can be concluded that Jambi Malays need conformity and harmony which is realized in the form of mutual love, happiness, economy, readiness, responsibility, courtesy, work, tranquility, humility, joy, maintaining good relationships, and living success.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Interlocking between Traditional Custody and Lembago of Jambi is part of the tradition in the traditional wedding procession owned by the Jambi Province community that needs to be developed, preserved, and passed down from generation to generation. In the traditional procession, not all skilled people act as actors representing the two parties as the spokesperson, namely the groom and the bride. There are certain people who understand about the stages of tradition that gives something special from the elders of groom side to the bride. The person that knows it clearly in the Jambi Malay tradition is called the elders or spokesperson.

Seloko used by the spokesperson contains various meanings, but not everyone understands the meaning. Most of them only understand as conversation smoothers or as a tradition only [Gafar, 2012]. Syam [2010] in Jambi custom, besides containing various meanings, seloko also contains advice and views of grandmothers, the elders, and clever people for the community. In addition, Gafar [2017] seloko also acts as a norm, philosophy, foundation, and affirmation in conveying the thoughts and feelings of the community and serves as a medium to create an atmosphere that is familiar and contains aesthetic value, a sense of ownership, honor and respect.

In the modern era, the tradition of Interlocking between Traditional Custody and Lembago of Jambi needs to be preserved and developed. This is because the marriage procession will be more

meaningful if this is done. The financial presence of the groom was also seen in the event. This can be seen from the luggage as a matter of custom, whether carrying a buffalo, a goat, or a chicken or in other terms buffalo-shaped buffalo, not goat-shaped goats or chicken-shaped chickens that have been put in boxes or envelopes.

The ceremony of that tradition in the Jambi Malay community is a very important event for every member of the community. "This sacred ceremony guides new families in the community and between families, and will change the structure of the community with its environment for the presence of new families" [Syam, 2010]. For this reason it must begin with full attention from parents, relatives, and the community so that the marriage is carried out in accordance with the prevailing customs.

2. BASELINE THEORY/MATERIALS/ METHODS

2.1 Baseline Theory

Nukman and Ikhsan [2012] state that seloko was created along with the Jambi Malay tradition with sense and ethics considerations as a social control full of meaning, both associative and lexical meanings. Kempson [1984] lexical meaning is the meaning that appears in the selection of words used by speakers. Leech [1987] has conceptual meaning and associative meaning which is divided into connotative meaning, social meaning, affective meaning, reflective meaning, collocative meaning and thematic meaning. Chaer [1995] states that lexical meaning is the meaning that corresponds to reality that is truly real in life. Whereas, Parera [1991] has interpretive meaning related to the interpretation and response of the reader or listener, writing or speaking, reading or listening. Meanwhile, Kridalaksana [1993] in addition to connotative meanings there are denotative meanings that are straightforward on something outside the language or based on certain conventions.

2.2 Material and Methods

The method used in this study is descriptive qualitative [Arikunto, 2006] with a content analysis and hermeneutic approach [Rohman, 2013]. As well as it is to obtain the validity of the data used techniques namely (1) theory triangulation, (2) methodology triangulation, and (3) expert triangulation. The data source used was Seloko in the marriage video of Fadilatul Hikmah with Alfarabi on February 4, 2017.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Ulur antar serah terimo adat dan lumbago (Interlocking between Traditional Custody and Lembago of Jambi), was one phase or step three of the eleven stages Jambi Malay traditional wedding procession and is also known by dropping *belanja* (shopping). The procession begins at 1. Kato bajawab in the courtyard between the progenitor or a spokesman for the groom and the bride and 2. Stepping up the ballroom, the event begins with 1) reading the Al-Quran, 2) chewing betel nut and smoking, 3) the elders of the bride handed conduction, 4) the elders of the bride check and receive conduction, 5) both parties have asked edict or opinion of the elders mediator, 6) customary procession received by all the parties, 7) determination of the marriage, 8) reading prayers, and 9) welcoming. Of these stages used *seloko adat*, except on step of reading Al-Qur'an, prayer and welcoming. Among the seloko can be seen along with its meaning as follows.

1. Kato Bajawab in the Yard

The sentence "*Nenek-mamak, tuo tengandai, cerdas pandai, alim ulama*" are conceptually have a meaning elder people, old people, smart people, theologians and by association means institution

of the elders, institutions of smart people, institution of religious people, which has an important role in society that should be respected and appreciated.

The sentence "*Induk-induk yang bersentuk cincin dijari nan bederau gelang di tangan*" conceptually means that the parents (mothers) are wearing a ring on her finger lots and lots of bracelets hand. While the associative meaning mothers who attended the event are the people respected, honorable, beautiful and dignified, as well as those who are economically disadvantaged.

The sentence "*berkain ujung serong, yang bersanggul lipat pandaan*" conceptually means that berkain and bersanggul neatly, while sesara associative means in accordance with customary rules and follow the way of dressing people respectable, neat, harmonious, fragrant and full of happiness.

The sentence "*anak mudo (youngest) capat kaki dan ringan tangan*" conceptually swift-footed meaningful way quickly and handily meaningful hands-down, while in associative swift-footed meaningless without prompting was gone and soft hands without prompting you for helping or doing work with full responsibility in completing the work.

2. Stepping Up the Hill

The sentence "*bukitlah kami daki, lurahlah kami turuni, unaklah kami ateh (potong)*" conceptually means that it is up the hill, already down a ravine, *cut unak* (midrib rattan prickly), whereas in associative means it's real effort despite various obstacles which must be passed to occupy the promise which He swore or to achieve the desired goal with the efforts and hard work.

The sentence "*lah putih mato kami dek memandang, lah ikal pulo rambut di kuduk, nek menengok lah pasak pulo tebing nek meninjau*" conceptually meaningful eyes were white because I have long looked at, hair, curly or frizzy did not get carded, land on the cliff was solid for trampled underfoot, while in associative significant long-awaited concerned does not come repeatedly, causing uncertainty and anxiety for those who wait, but still show calmness.

The sentence "*ibarat orang bepikat ayam lah terdengar kukuknyo, ibarat orang nembaklah tepat nian sasarannyo*" conceptually meaningful voice chicken has been heard and shooting has been on target, while the meaning of associative as person or guest / prospective groom awaited imminent at home prospective bride the woman and the house targeted by a candidate or party bride is not one house or address so that the hearts were dropping and the host was elated.

1) Chewing Betel Nut and Smoking

The sentence "*bukanlah kami nak bauji samo merah, bekati nak samo berat, dak pulo budi nak babalas kasih kan batimbal*" conceptually meaningful not want to test the same red, scales the weight and not return the favor, by association means the host preparing betel Foreword and cigarettes for food, this kind of thing is not for payback but according to the customs and habits of every guest who comes to be fed before asked for what purposes these guests come, this is also done for the courtesy and mutual respect.

The sentence "*kok betemu dengan yang besawar jangan ditempuh, kok betemu dengan yang berebo jangan diungkai*" conceptually means do not pass in a *bersawar* (fencing) and *berebo* (wood in the forest had been cleared but not yet cut) do not *diungkai* (cleaned) whereas the meaning asosiatifnya do not break the rules, etiquette, customs, and cultures, if violated will incur customary law or customs debt as a form of social responsibility.

2) The Elders from the Groom Parties Submitting Conduction

The sentence "*bak kayu gedang ditengah negeri, daunnyo rindang tempat kito beteduh, dahanyo kuat tempat kito begantung, batangnyo gedang tempat kito bersandar, akarnyo kokoh tepat kito duduk besilo*" conceptually means there was a large wooden in the middle country from another

wood, leaves dense, branches strong hung, the great stem lean, its roots are strong for the seat, while meanings associative symbolize their rulers, or community leaders are very influential for the community to be a place to ask for protection, rescue, and footing both morally and materially or economy in public life.

The sentence "*maklumlah kedatangan kami tadi banyak, lah penuh laman yang ujo, lah mendesak laman yang panjang, rumah nan gedang, mungkin di antaro kami ado yang salah langkah, tangan salah limbai, lidah salah kato*" conceptually meaningful people come a lot, yard extensive is full, long page is already packed, big house, one step, one to work the hand, one speaks, by association means people who come (most of people) find themselves a lot of flaws and errors that are not desired by the host or the parties come which could lead to the wrong place themselves, one by custom or ketersingungan with the words spoken by immigrants the bridegroom to the bride women, it also aims to maintain the propriety and love.

The sentence "*sebagai ulasan jari sambungan tangan, sebagai ulasan kata penyambung lidah*" conceptually means that finger for reviews and hands are connected, said reviews and tongue are connected, but conceptually means that as a messenger of the bridegroom to convey something and as spokesperson to convey the intent and desire of the bridegroom and the bride so well on women as a form of humility.

The sentence "*dimano bumi dipijak, disitu langit di junjung, dimano tembilang dicacak disitu tanaman tumbuh*" conceptually means that Rome, do the Romans, tembilang dicacak and plants grow, by association means someone must conform to the rules of customs, culture, rules that apply everywhere where he was to maintain good relations.

The sentence "*mempunyai anak bujang, itu ibarat harimau di ujung tanjung, dio mengaung kesano, mengaum kesini, tabilo-bilo dio lapar*". "Having girls as the custom is like a fire on a reed, if ado angin blown little burnt" conceptually means that having children flunky like tigers at the tip of the promontory sounded here and there, who knows when he is hungry, has a girl like fire on reed, if the wind a little burned out. By association means that boys have the freedom of roaming around but that freedom must be supervised by their parents not to do that is not good for the girl child. When this happens it will cause havoc and disgrace to the old person on this sigadis especially for older people.

The sentence "*strong wind was the commandment of the timber will be uprooted, aek heavy pounding the cliff, cliffs will crumble*" conceptually means that agin tight timber will fall, cliffs pounded jetted will collapse, by association means that in order to get the desired one must dare to sacrifice anything, Therefore, he must prepare himself properly so as not to drift improper harm himself.

The sentence "*kalu mudik kami lah bagalah, ilir bagalah santang*" conceptually means that going home to put on pole, Iilir to wear satang, by association means to achieve something must be assisted with a variety of equipment and items should be adjusted to its usefulness.

3) The Elders from the Bride Checking And Receiving Gift

The sentence "*kok harilah beganti hari, minggu lah beganti bulan, bahkan bulanlah menjadi tahun*" conceptually means that day by day, weeks turned into months, months turned into years, by association means that the time to wait, wait, and hope that never fulfilled as which are expected.

The sentence "*Kalu jauh mungkin nak kami tinjau. Kok dekat nak kami pegang. Seandainya betali tentu nak kami tarik. Seandainya kalu betampuk nak kami jinjing*" conceptually means that the conduction brought the men there are distant and some are close. By association means that the conduction delivered the men have not been so apparent to the elders of the bride in this case is examine what is delivered or carried.

The sentence "*nak kami sisik siang dulu nenek mamak, akan kami sisik sampai ke tunggul, lah kami siang sampai ke tunas*" conceptual meaning contained in this Seloko means cleaning gardens to complete a thorough cleansing. While the associative that conduction brought by the groom examined one by one and nothing is left behind.

4) The Elders from Both Parties Asked Edict or Opinion of the Elders of Mediator

The sentence "*Makannyo habis, minumnyo mengering, nyincangnyo memutus, dan menentukan sah dengan batalnyo*" conceptually means that eating should be discharged, drinking should be dry, cutting must break, determine the legitimacy with the cancellation of a work to be done by the elders. By association means all negotiations between the elders from men and women, as well as conduction provided must obtain approval and ratification of the elders arbitrator. They decide the admissibility of such negotiations or conduction.

The sentence "*Kok lebar lah dilipat, kok panjang lah digulung, ado dalam kotak yang sebuah iko*" conceptually means that the folded width, length was coiled, is in the box. By association means that conduction in the form of goods that should have been replaced in another form, namely in the form of money that is described by the sentence fold and roll is already in the box.

The Sentence "*Kami mengharapkan kepada nenek-mamak, kurang yang perlu ditambah, patah yang perlu disisip*" conceptually means that the elders expecting something less needs to be added, broken need to be repair. In associative meaning all talks or less conduction, which needs to be supplemented and corrected in accordance with customary rules. The sentence "*lah banyak laut yang direnaginyo, banyak pulo kampung yang dijelajahinyo, banyak pulo gelangan yang dicubonyo*" conceptually means that the elders's spokesman both sides was a lot of sea to be swum, many village that already explored, and more arena that already tried. By association means that the elders mediator give praise to the elders both sides, that they have a lot of experience about stalling handover between customs and institutions.

The sentence "*titian teras bertanggo batu, dak lekang dek panas, dak lapuk dek hujan*" conceptually means that there is a bridge that is strong made of stone, heat resistance, not weathered by rain. by association means that a household will go well and survive old should be based on honesty, harmony, mutual trust, and resistant to the rumors and slander that struck and need to stay in one direction.

The sentence "*panjang rambut besak sanggulnyo, kalu pendek rambuk kecil sanggulnyo*" conceptually means that if makes a bun in long hair it will be a big bun, if short hair so it will be small bun. by association means that the existence of the economic of men will be seen by their gift. If it is big it means the economic condition of the groom is good and vise versa.

The sentence "*kalu nak tau di luar negeri tanyo dengan burung elang, kalu nak tau dalamnyo aek tanyo dengan berang-berang, kalu nak tau panjangnyo pantai tanyo ikan seluang*" conceptually means that there are hawks clever, there are beavers who know it water, and there are fish that knows the length of the beach, by association means that if you want to ask about something let asked the experts.

The sentence "*Adat di atas tumbuh, lembago di atas tuah*" conceptually means that customary institutions evolve and auspicious, by association significantly when the prospective groom capable of filling custom should not be limited, it is also symbolized by the filling custom, wore two clothes, which are wet and dry. it indicates that it comes ready to provide a living and unseen. As well as the cast institution one buffalo, rice 100 bushels, coconut 100 rope, sweet and salt.

5) The Customary Procession Accepted By All Parties

Poem "*dari Muaro Buat ke Batang Asai, singah berhenti di Dusun Karak, gawe adat sudah selesai, mau dicepat-cepatkan gawe sarak*" Conceptually means that custom work has been

completed and continued work Sarak, by association means faster is better that there should be things that are not desirable and accelerate the good work will be rewarded.

Poem “*dak ado lagi tanah bapingkah, lah ketemu tanah bapayo, dak ado lagi cakap yang batingkah, lah ketemu kato yang seiyo*” conceptually means that the land is no longer cracked, existing brackish soil, speech has been agreed, the words already in one direction. by association means the agreement is complete, custom conduction has been received and all the elders of both parties and the mediator have agreed there is no gap again to debate and accept everything what is negotiated.

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Ulur antar serah terimo adat dan lumbago starting with 1. Kato bajawab in the courtyard between the progenitor or a spokesman for the groom and the bride and 2. Stepping up the ballroom, the event begins with 1) reading the Al-Quran, 2) chewing betel nut and smoking, 3) the elders of the bride handed conduction, 4) the elders of the bride check and receive conduction, 5) both parties have asked edict or opinion of the elders mediator, 6) customary procession received by all the parties, 7) determination of the marriage, 8) reading prayers, and 9) welcoming.

From the stages of these activities are found meaning in the form of love, courage, happiness, economy, happiness, readiness, responsible, well-mannered, jobs, serenity, humility, joy, maintain good relationships, and life success.

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THE ROLE OF CIVIC EDUCATION IN THE FORMATION OF NATION CHARACTERS, AS EDUCATION INTRODUCTION TO THE STATE

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Abstract

The existence of citizenship education is very important in forming human beings with character and have a strong state defense attitude, but seeing from the material that is abundant but not balanced with adequate time allocation, of course this will have an inadequacy and not yet embedded love and defense A high country, so efforts need to be made so that this lecture is not just a symbol, but it is hoped that it can be a problem solving of the existing problems. the hope of implementing the values of the nation's ideological values must always be mobilized in echoing from kindergartens to tertiary institutions, the phenomenon that there is citizenship education with existing material content is thought to have not been able to instill a sense of nationalism and state defense The existence of Citizenship Education has a very important role and function in shaping the behavior of Indonesian students by incorporating it into the education system they hold, it is hoped that its citizens will become smart citizens and good citizens who know and realize fully their rights as citizens, as well as knowing and being fully responsible for their obligations towards the safety of their nation and country. Citizenship Education (PKn) developed in Indonesia should also be able to rediscover the relevance of the fundamental values of society with rapidly changing social dynamics. By teaching Civics, it should not only be a matter of cognitive issues, but must provide a moral and social action touch. As a preliminary education, the defense of citizenship education plays a very strategic role in efforts to shape the nation's character.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Citizenship education plays an important role for the State in order to prepare intelligent, responsible and know their own citizens. The terminology of this course is different in every country that mentions civic education, citizenship education, and some even call democracy education Based on the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education system and the Decree of the Director General of Higher Education Ministry of National Education Number 43 / DIKTI / Kep / 2006 concerning Implementation Signposts for Personality Development courses in universities, civic education is a subject must be given in all faculties and all departments throughout universities in the archipelago The citizenship education that was developed certainly cannot be separated from its basis, namely Pancasila which is used as a source of all sources of law in our country As stated (Mansoer, 2005) the philosophy of Pancasila contains the contents of Indonesia's national identity and the content of the meaning of the preliminary education of State defense Based on the fact, the awareness of the importance of the rights and obligations of citizens as well as the awareness of democracy must always be fostered and implemented in real life, in family life, in a nation and state society.

In line with these expectations, of course the hope of implementing the values of the nation's ideology must always be mobilized in echoing from kindergartens to universities, the

phenomenon that there is citizenship education with material content that is now thought to have not been able to instill a sense of nationalism and a sense of national defense.

For this reason, this article limits the discussion on the role of civic education / civic education in the formation of national character as part of the preliminary education to defend the state. The purpose of this writing is as expected to provide both theoretical and practical benefits that are useful for the development of knowledge and provide input to stakeholders to make policies.

1. The results of this academic study will certainly be useful in enriching the education discipline more specifically contributing to the development of learning methods.
2. Practically the results of this study are useful for lecturers to further improve competence in lectures on civic education

2. EXISTENCE OF CITIZENSHIP EDUCATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONALITY

2.1 CIVIC EDUCATION

Citizenship education in universities is presented with separate lectures separated from Pancasila education, basically the same as civic education, namely how to make good citizenship. Citizenship Education is an effort to equip students with basic knowledge and abilities regarding the relationship between citizens and the state to become citizens that can be relied upon by the nation and the state. Successful Citizenship Education will produce a mental attitude that is intelligent and full of responsibility from students through Citizenship Education, citizens of the Republic of Indonesia are expected to be able to understand, analyze and answer the problems faced by society, the nation and the country on an ongoing basis and be consistent with their national ideals and goals as outlined in the opening of the 1945 Constitution. In filling independence and facing globalization, every citizen of the Republic of Indonesia in general and students in particular must remain on their identity who are patriotic and patriotic in the non-physical struggle in accordance with their respective professions in all aspects of life.

Citizenship Education is all things related to citizens both empirical and non-empirical, in the form of insight, attitudes and behavior of citizens in the Republic of Indonesia. Citizenship Education has a very important role and function in shaping the behavior of Indonesian students by including them in the education system they hold, it is hoped that their citizens will become smart citizens and good citizens who know and are fully aware of their rights as citizens, as well as knowing and being fully responsible for their obligations towards the safety of their nation and country. Thus the granting of Citizenship Education will give birth to citizens who have high souls and patriotism and nationalism. In general, civic education carried out by various countries aims and aims so that the citizens of the nation re-explore the basic values, history and future of the nation in accordance with the most fundamental values (basic state) adopted by the nation that concerned. In line with this fact, the essence of Civics which is one part of personality courses must prioritize the affective aspects among students. The philosophical foundation and hope above, then need to find its relevance to the conditions and challenges of real life in society, so that Citizenship Education is able to contribute positively to solving social problems that are being faced by a nation or society. Therefore, whatever form of Citizenship Education developed in various nations, it is very necessary to develop the fundamental values of the nation (society) in accordance with the dynamics of social change, so that the foundational values find their relevance to contribute significantly to the problems of society, the nation. Citizenship (PKn) developed in Indonesia should also be able to rediscover the relevance of the fundamental values

of society with rapidly changing social dynamics. By teaching Civics, it should not only be a matter of cognitive issues, but must provide a moral and social action touch.

This moral and social action touch must receive greater attention, so that the teaching of Civics is able to reach its goals and objectives, namely to shape students into good and responsible citizens.

Indeed, when the founder of the Republic stipulated Article 31 paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution which obliged "the Government to strive for and administer a national teaching system", it was intended that education was designed, especially school education, to give birth to Indonesian citizens who supported the development of an intelligent nation of life. In other words, national education is essentially citizenship education in order to produce good quality Indonesian citizens in disciplines, both social discipline and national discipline, in the work ethic, in work productivity, in intellectual ability, professional / or vocational ability, in a sense of community responsibility nationality and humanity, as well as morality, character and personality. Quality human beings like this are expected to be produced by the education process and school Citizenship Education is developed in education in higher education because it is a conscious effort to prepare students through guidance and / or training activities in order to develop or foster awareness, love, loyalty and courage to sacrifice in order to defend the nation and country. As well as aiming for the nation's citizens to explore the basic values, history and future of the nation in accordance with the values of the pali

2.2 THE EXISTENCE OF CITIZENSHIP EDUCATION FORMS THE NATION'S PERSONALITY

In the opinion of the author the existence of citizenship education is very important in shaping human beings who have character and have a strong state defense attitude, but seeing from the material that is numerous but not balanced with adequate time allocation, of course this will have an inadequate impact and not yet embedded high love and defense of the State, so efforts need to be made so that this lecture is not just a symbol but it is hoped that it can be a problem solving of every problem that exists, because as we know the character of the nation which has begun to be eroded by the culture of the outside culture, waning sense of solidarity among others, the development of racism, understanding radicalism.

To take care of all these problems is certainly not as easy as turning the palm of the hand, the reform era marked by the fall of the new order government is our embryo to restore the implementation of the 1945 constitution purely and consistently, one of which is safely amended to the 1945 Constitution.

Aside from that, Pancasila and citizenship education as a preliminary education for martial arts need to be instilled from an early age, up to college, by integrating preliminary education to defend the country with compulsory military practice, so here students do not study theory theory but are accompanied by practice and mental formation the tough one. As a real example, holding a flag ceremony every month, wearing costumes that show our identity like batik and they are also taught with marching physical exercises.

Intense ideas carried out by the government through the four pillars of nationality are programs that can maintain the integrity of the nation in this increasingly competitive era, the value of noble values need to be made as a reference and guidance for every citizen in the life of nation and state.

1. Pancasila
2. Bhineka Tunggal ika
3. The 1945 Constitution
4. The Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia

Every nation has its identity. By understanding the nation's identity, it is expected to understand the national identity so as to foster pride as a nation. In this discussion, certainly cannot ignore the discussion of past and present conditions, between ideality and reality and between the *das Sollen* and *das Sein*.

The character comes from the Latin "karakter, kharassein or kharax", in French "caractere" in English "character. In the broadest sense of character means the nature of psychology, character, character, character, character that distinguishes someone from others (National Team Lecturer for Citizenship Education, 2011: 67). Thus the character of the nation can be interpreted as a typical Indonesian character or character that distinguishes the Indonesian nation from other nations.

According to Max Weber (quoted by Darmaputra, 1988: 3) the best way to understand a society is to understand the behavior of its members. And the way to understand the behavior of members is to understand their culture that is their system of meaning. Humans are creatures who always seek continuous meaning for all their actions. The meaning is always the orientation of human actions whether consciously or not. Humans also seek and try to explain 'logic' of the social behavior of certain communities through their own culture. In developing societies or Third World societies, generally face three main problems namely nation-building, political stability and economic development. Nation-building is a problem that relates to the inheritance of the past, how diverse communities try to build shared unity. Political stability is a problem related to the current reality of the threat of disintegration. While the problem of economic development is a problem related to the future, namely (in the Indonesian context) a just and prosperous society (Darmaputra, 1988: 5).

We have no doubt about the existence of Pancasila as a fundamental norm, the Pancasila that was born from a long formulation by the founding father has succeeded in uniting the values of life that grow and develop in the middle of Indonesian society, from Sabang to Merauke. Diversity as the strength of the Indonesian Nation which must always be maintained Diversity should we understand as a unifying force of a nation whose existence cannot be denied. Diversity must also be interpreted by the community through understanding multiculturalism based on the power of spirituality. The power of spirituality here means that society sees that difference as a unifying diversity, accepting difference as a force not as a threat or interference. All existing cultures, religions & tribes remain in their respective forms, what unites is the sense of nationalism of pride as an Indonesian nation that has hundreds of cultures, customs, customs.

Diversity is a unifying pillar of the nation that must be viewed with pride, pride because we can be separated from narrow primordialism which considers race, adat, other religions to be inferior / worse than personal property. The compartmentalization of this element of society is the fruit of the Dutch colonial era that used the war tactic "devide et impera".

The attitude and view of the narrow primordiariness will bring Indonesia to the destruction & disintegration of the nation. Horizontal conflict (between communities) often occurs due to trivial & trivial matters, to bring problems to SARA. Sad & apprehensive for a country the size of Indonesia which had been independent 73 years ago it was always compartmentalizing the elements of society to the smallest things. Unity in Diversity It cannot be considered merely a slogan, but it is lived in life, kept in the heart of every Indonesian citizen to maintain the unity of the state. In principle, the slogan of the Indonesian people has a very important meaning, namely tolerance and unity. First, tolerance can dissolve differences into unity so that there are no divisions or conflicts. Second, Unity is something that must be done in realizing unity and unity of various races, tribes, and religions The 1945 Constitution of the 1945 Constitution is interpreted as a written Constitution or a basic charter which contains the principle that contains norms for the implementation of state government.

3. CONCLUSION

From the discussion above we can conclude that in general Understanding Citizenship Education in Higher Education is one of the efforts to revive the national spirit of the younger generation, especially students, in facing the influence of globalization and to strengthen awareness of defending the country. which is very strategic in the effort to form the character of the nation, character or character can only be formed and developed through the educational process, it is not possible with teaching. The aim of Understanding Citizenship Education in Higher Education is to foster awareness of basic obligations in the defense of the state with a nation and state that has an integral comprehensive mindset.

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ANALYSIS OF VALUE EFFECTIVENESS MACHINE USING OVERALL EQUIPMENT EFFECTIVENESS (OEE) METHOD AS AN IMPROVEMENT TO MINIMIZE SIX BIG LOSSES IN STEEL INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Machine is very vital and important role in the production line manufacturing of steel industry. The machine maintenance system has a constraint on the old machine which caused the level of productivity decreased. The purpose of this research is to measure and find the level of machine effectiveness, also to offer solutions to improve the effectiveness of the machine by calculating Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) which consists of several components such as availability ratio, performance ratio, and quality ratio of the production process. Further, to be able to acknowledge the most influential losses in the production line and assist the company to decide its policy appropriately as an effort to repair the machine using Six Big Losses. The OEE calculation of the Electrolytic Cleaning Line 1 (ECL-1) in Plant Cold Rolling Mill (CRM) is 64.91% which is still below the standard World Class OEE of 85%. While the significant losses result in Reduce Speed Losses factor of 19.80%. Based on analysis using fishbone diagram, it shows machine speed decreasing by ECL-1 that is caused by factor of machine, material, and method.

DOI :

1. INTRODUCTION

The industry world manufacturing is growing up very rapidly. Every company always makes change in a continuous improvement in each department to be able to compete in the era of globalization, especially in the production line. production line has various things that must always be improved, including equipment and machines that support the production process. the effort to repair on the manufacturing world, in terms of equipment and machine are to increase the utilization of existing equipment as optimal as possible. Utilization of existing equipment on the average manufacturing industry is half of the real machine capability [1]. A company makes a lot of improvements. but in the fact, many company did not focused on the root causes and lot of waste occur. Eventually many losses occur such as time, costs, and most problems. thus, a method is needed that can be increase according to the problem of lack of equipment productivity. In this research implement Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) method is a method that uses several manufacturing units which are then divided into 3 important parameters such as availability, performance rate and quality rate [2]. So that the component of OEE is a key index for a production [3]. In the OEE concept is measuring the ability of machine by showing scope of specific improvements. Where the statistical data collected from output plant becomes useful information for increasing the area. [4]In finding identification which the most significant causes of failure of OEE values, researchers used Six Big Losses. Where the determinants are categorized

into 3, namely downtime losses, speed losses, and defect losses. [5] This research was conducted on the company PT. XYZ which is a manufacturing company that produces steel. In the production line, the engine has decreased the level of productivity due to the age of the old machine. To be able to make improvements in accordance with the problems that occur by calculating OEE which is part of the Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) method and using Six Big Losses to determine the losses that most influence the low OEE value, then analyze the causes of losses by using the fishbone diagram and provide solutions relating to the losses that occur.

2. BASIC THEORY

2.1 Total Productive Maintenance (TPM)

Total Productive Maintenance is a productive maintenance development from America which was adopted later by Japan. In the technique TPM is used to be a maintenance team in an organization that involves human resources in a strategy-based on company designed to maximize the effectiveness of equipment by developing a comprehensive maintenance production system. The main objective is to realize cost saving through maintenance and increased machine productivity. [6]

2.2 Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE)

Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) is a method used to measure the level of effectiveness of the use of a machine tool so that it can provide an overview of whether the equipment has worked optimally or not. OEE is known as one of the applications of the Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) program because this tool can find out the problems in the equipment. In measuring the effectiveness value of an equipment or machine, it can be calculated by the following formula:

$$OEE(\%) = Availability\ Ratio \times Performance\ Efficiency \times Rate\ of\ Quality$$

The effective value of an equipment in Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) according to the Japan Institute of Plan Maintenance (JIPM). In a company must have an ideal value of world class of 85% or more ideal value. In the calculation and measurement using OEE, there are 3 types of losses that are directly related to the production process that must be anticipated, namely:

2.2.1 Availability Ratio

Availability Ratio is the ratio between the actual operating time and the loading time. This value can describe the level of readiness of existing and used tools to operate. Low availability is reflection of poor maintenance. In simple terms and basis for calculating the Availability ratio as follows:

$$Availability\ Ratio(\%) = \frac{Load\ time - downtime}{load\ time} \times 100\%$$

Explanation:

- Loading Time: Time available to carry out the production process
- Downtime: Time lost due to engine damage

2.2.2. Performance Ratio

Performance Ratio is a ratio that describes the ability of equipment in producing goods. Three important factors are needed to calculate performance efficiency, there are:

- Ideal cycle time
- Total output (Output standard + Output non standard)
- Operating Time (Loading time – downtime)

The following is the formula for determining the level of performance efficiency:

$$\text{Performance Rate} = \frac{\text{Ideal cycle time} \times \text{Total Output}}{\text{Operating time}} \times 100\%$$

2.2.3 Quality Ratio

This measurement is used to determine the quality of production, whether a machine can produce products with results or quality determined by the company or not. So, the ability of the machine to produce products that meet these quality requirements depends on the condition of the machine, whether it is ready for use or not. In addition, the capability factor of the operator also plays an important role in every production produced by the machine. The rate of quality is calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{Rate of Quality} = \frac{\text{Total output} - \text{Output non standard}}{\text{Total output}} \times 100\%$$

Explanation:

- Total Output : $\text{Output standard} + \text{Output non standard}$
- Output Standard : Products that are in accordance with the specified quality
- Non standard: Products that are in not accordance with the specified quality

2.2.4 Six Big Losses

The purpose of six big losses is to find out the loss factors that provide the biggest contribution in reducing the productivity of machines in the production line. The analysis carried out is that there are large loss factors such as breakdown losses, set up & adjustment, idling and loss losses, reduced speed losses, reduce yield losses, defect losses. [7]

2.2.5 Fishbone Diagram

fishbone diagram is a visual tool such as a fish fin which is used to identify and sort systematically the root causes of different problems so that the diagram can provide several causes of the effects of the biggest problem. [8]

3 RESEACRH METHODS

This research aim is to measure the effectiveness of one machine at the plant of the company PT. XYZ. Using OEE method approach. Researchers make observations in advance to retrieve data. The data obtained are production data, product data, and utilization data of cold rolling mill plants (CRM). After the data is obtained, then do the data processing also analysis of Six big losses are carried out as well as suggestion for improvement for the company.

4 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Analysis of OEE Result

In determining the formula and measuring the effectiveness of the machine, OEE using 3 aspects are multiplying the value of Availability Ratio, Performance Ratio, and Quality Ratio. So, the following are the results obtained from 3 aspects of OEE:

Table 1 Availability Ratio Results

Month	Operating Time		Loading Time		Availability Ratio (%)		
	Lite	Medium	Lite	Medium	Lite	Medium	Average
January	8,426.25	10,111.50	8,781.25	10,537.50	95.96%	95.96%	95.96%

Month	Operating Time		Loading Time		Availability Ratio (%)		
	Lite	Medium	Lite	Medium	Lite	Medium	Average
February	7,759.50	9,311.40	8,116.00	9,739.20	95.61%	95.61%	95.61%
March	7,601.50	9,121.80	8,203.75	9,844.50	92.66%	92.66%	92.66%
April	8,695.75	10,434.90	9,191.25	11,029.50	94.61%	94.61%	94.61%
Mei	9,522.50	11,427.00	10,571.25	12,685.50	90.08%	90.08%	90.08%
June	9,647.75	11,577.30	10,033.00	12,039.60	96.16%	96.16%	96.16%
Total					94.18%	94.18%	94.18%

This following is the formula used to measure availability ratio and an example of the calculation availability ratio for the Lite type in January 2017:

$$Availability = \frac{Operating\ Time}{Loading\ Time} \times 100\%$$

$$Availability\ Ratio = \frac{8,426.25}{8,781.25}$$

$$= 95,96\%$$

Table 2 Performance Efficiency Results

Month	Total Output (Coil)		Cycle Time (Coil/Minute)	Operating Time (Minute)		Performance Efficiency (%)		
	Lite	Medium		Lite	Medium	Lite	Medium	Average
January	342.71	411.25	Lite: 24.40	84,26.25	10,111.5	99.24%	74.35%	86.79%
February	307.45	368.94		7,759.5	9,311.4	96.68%	72.43%	84.55%
March	259.10	310.91		7,601.5	9,121.8	83.17%	62.31%	72.74%
April	260.73	312.87	Medium: 18.28	8,695.75	10,434.9	73.16%	54.81%	63.98%
Mei	355.39	426.47		9,522.5	11,427	91.06%	68.22%	79.64%
June	366.99	477.88		9,647.75	11,577.3	92.81%	75.46%	88.09%

This following is the formula used to measure performance ratio and an example of the calculation performance efficiency for the Lite type in Mei 2017:

$$Performance\ Efficiency = \frac{Total\ Output \times Cycle\ Time}{Operating\ Time} \times 100\%$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Performance Efficiency} &= \frac{355.39 \times 24.40}{9,522.5} 100\% \\ &= 91.06\% \end{aligned}$$

Table 3 Rate of Quality Results

Month	Total of Good Product (Coil)		Total Production (Coil)		Rate of Quality (%)		
	<i>Lite</i>	<i>Medium</i>	<i>Lite</i>	<i>Medium</i>	<i>Lite</i>	<i>Medium</i>	Average
January	289.43	347.32	342.71	411.25	84.45%	84.45%	84.45%
February	280.50	336.60	307.45	368.94	91.23%	91.23%	91.23%
March	236.76	284.11	259.10	310.91	91.38%	91.38%	91.38%
April	229.17	275.01	260.73	312.87	87.90%	87.90%	87.90%
Mei	267.76	321.32	355.39	426.47	75.34%	75.34%	75.34%
June	359.82	431.78	398.24	477.88	90.35%	90.35%	90.35%

This following is the formula used to measure Rate of Quality and an example of the calculation Rate of Quality for the Lite type in March 2017:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate of Quality} &= \frac{\text{Total of Good Product}}{\text{Total Production}} \times 100\% \\ \text{Rate of Quality} &= \frac{236.76}{259.10} \times 100\% \\ &= 91.38\% \end{aligned}$$

After getting value of the Availability Ratio, Performance Efficiency, and Rate of Quality, then the value of Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) can be calculated every month to determine the effectiveness of the use Electrolytic Cleaning Line 1 (ECL-1) machines in Cold Rolling Mill Plant (CRM) The formula used to calculate OEE is:

$$\text{OEE} = \text{Availability Ratio} \times \text{Performance Efficiency} \times \text{Rate of Quality}$$

Table 4 Overall Equipment Effectiveness

Month	Availability Ratio (%)	Performance Efficiency (%)	Rate of Quality (%)	OEE (%)
January	95.96%	86.79%	84.45%	70.34%
February	95.61%	84.55%	91.23%	73.75%
March	92.66%	72.74%	91.38%	61.59%
April	94.61%	63.98%	87.90%	53.21%
Mei	90.08%	79.64%	75.34%	54.05%
June	96.16%	88.09%	90.35%	76.53%
Average	94.18%	79.30%	86.78%	64.91%

Whereas the more detailed description of the Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) results for each type of product contained in the CRM plant are:

Table 5 Product Types of Overall Equipment Effectiveness Results

Month	Product Types		Average
	Lite	Medium	
January	80.42%	60.25%	70.34%
February	84.33%	63.18%	73.75%
March	70.42%	52.76%	61.59%
April	60.84%	45.58%	53.21%
Mei	61.80%	46.30%	54.05%
June	87.51%	65.56%	76.53%
Average	74.22%	55.60%	64.91%

Based on the results of the calculation of data, the Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) value was obtained on the ECL-1 machine on the CRM plant which was 64.91%.

Figure 1 Graph of Overall Equipment Effectiveness ECL-1 Machine

According to the figure 4.5, Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) on the ECL-1 machine has a rather bad value. PT. XYZ has averaged during half semester of 2017 and the show end result is below the ideal value. The Ideal value refers to the value of the world class benchmark standard recommended by the Japan Institute of Plant Maintenance (JIPM) that for the Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) is 85%.

4.2 Analysis of Six Big Losses Results

Analysis of the six big losses calculation is used to determine six factors of big losses that the most contribute within the decrease machine productivity. Electrolytic Cleaning Line 1 (ECL-1) in the Cold Rolling Mill (CRM) plant.

Figure 2. Pareto Chart of Six Big Losses

The results of the six big losses are presented on the Pareto chart, it is known the biggest losses that caused of OEE has low idela value is Speed Losses Reduce factor with percent 47.1%. Reduce Speed Losses is a decrease in production speed that come up if the actual operating speed is smaller than the speed of engine that has been designed to operate on speed normal.

4.3 Analysis of Fishbone *Reduce Speed Losses*

The following is a fishbone that illustrates the cause of the high losses of reduce speed losses on the six big losses.

Figure 3. Fishbone

Based on the fishbone diagram, it is known that the cause of the high value of losses due the reduce speed losses on the Electrolytic Clean Line (ECL-1) machine consists of three main factors. There are the engine, material and method factors.

5. CONCLUSION

According to the above analysis, the researcher can make conclusions:

1. The level of effectiveness ECL-1 machine in the Cold Rolling Mill Plant (CRM) based on calculations using the Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) method which is 64.91%. if refer to the OEE ideal by the Japan Institute of Plant Maintenance (JIPM) of 85%, the level of effectiveness of ECL-1 machine is still below from ideal or can be called

- not optimal. However, based on the results of an analysis that considers the age of the machine has reached 30 years, it can be known that the OEE value is quite good.
2. Based on six big losses analysis, it is known that the root of main problem which caused by the level of effectiveness ECL-1 machine is bellow from ideal standard JIPM. The loss is found on Reduce Speed Losses with 19.80% or in the Pareto chart is 47.1 %. Meanwhile, the cause of the ECL-1 machine speed reduction is caused by machine, material and method factors.
 3. As for some suggestion to solve the research is re-evaluation of maintenance scheduling to find out a effectiveness, using spare parts with good quality, more careful supervision to minimize the risk of coil breakdown when machine speed is increased, and also making plan for related innovations or improvements that need to be done to improve effectiveness and productivity of ECL-1 machines.

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